

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL-PROFESSIONAL MOBILITY OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10436184>

Abstract. *This article discusses the pedagogical conditions for the development of socio-professional mobility of future teachers, technological culture, as well as the level of formation of metaprofessional qualities and basic competencies of a university graduate's successful adaptation to the conditions of professional activity.*

Keywords: *Mobility, socio-professional mobility, metasubject, technological culture, professional value.*

Important changes taking place in all spheres of social and spiritual life have a unique effect on the state of modern education. It can be seen that the efficiency of specialists' work is determined by the level of personal and professional compliance with the specific nature of professional reality. In this regard, the issue of specific features of pedagogical conditions to increase the socio-professional mobility of future teachers and their personal development is of particular relevance. The latter is defined as the process and result of the formation of professionally important characteristics of a specialist, which is the system of his values and emotional relationships that affect the effectiveness of professional activity. This system includes:

- The main professional value is proper professional activity within the chosen specialty;

Important professional values (professional mobility; creative self-awareness in the profession; interpersonal communication; compliance with the professional image);

Supporting professional values and emotional attitudes (critical attitude to one's professional knowledge; cognitive interest in theoretical aspects of professional activity; recognition of the high importance of the profession in society, etc.).

The main goal of the pedagogical system for the development of social and professional mobility of a specialist is to create favorable conditions for the formation of competitive specialists with different levels of social and professional mobility, distinguished by professional skills, professional culture and reflection. Also, high professional flexibility in the labor market.

The process of developing socio-professional mobility of future specialists in the study of humanitarian sciences can be shown as a strategy implemented on the basis of the principles specific to this process. Among them, in addition to the generally recognized principles (scientific character; relevance of education to life; education and development; convenience) principles are also included [3]:

1. Continuity of education, which implies the unity of all stages of the development process of socio-professional mobility of future specialists in the study of humanitarian sciences;

2. Consistency, which allows considering all the planned elements of the social-professional mobility development system as a whole with various internal connections between

themselves and the external environment, reflects the completeness of the necessary forms in the educational activity of the university.

3. Humanitarianism is manifested in the strengthening of humanitarianism.

Based on the interests of forming the main elements of socio-professional mobility, the direction of training a specialist, revealing his personal potential;

4. The dynamism expressed in constant anticipation of new trends and changes in professional activity, as well as the needs of the labor market, reflects them in the process of developing social and professional mobility of future specialists;

5. Individualization and differentiation, taking into account their needs, interests, inclinations and abilities, as well as directing the development of the individual's creative beginnings in the implementation of the system of development of socio-professional mobility of future specialists.

Interdisciplinary relations that suggest relations between the subjects of fundamental and humanitarian education in the process of forming the metasubject foundations of social and professional mobility of the future specialist.

The following conceptual rules are derived from the above: the purpose of the process of development of socio-professional mobility of future specialists is determined by the requirements of modernity, taking into account the prospective trends of economic development.

The successful adaptation of a university graduate to the conditions of professional activity is determined by the level of formation of metaprofessional qualities and basic competencies:

- ensuring the socio-professional mobility of the future specialist implies the development of a scientifically based model of the process of the development of socio-professional mobility, the creation of pedagogical conditions and appropriate technology for its implementation.

- when speaking directly about the pedagogical conditions for the development of socio-professional mobility, it is necessary to define the concepts of "condition" and "pedagogical conditions".

In the philosophical encyclopedic dictionary, the concept of "condition" is defined as follows: "A condition is something that depends on something else (conditional), is an important component of a complex of objects, the existence of which requires the realization of this event ". [4]

Pedagogical conditions are defined in modern didactics as a set of factors that ensure the success of education, components of the educational process. Let's consider the pedagogical conditions proposed in the research hypothesis for the development of the social and professional mobility of the future foreign language teacher at the higher educational institution of pedagogy.

Acquiring technological culture is important for the development of social and professional mobility for future foreign language teachers. Today, the activity of young foreign language teachers is not sufficiently developed. Many university graduates do not always have the opportunity to apply the knowledge gained during the introduction of new alternative pedagogical technologies, to perform professional functions. In addition, they face great difficulties in adapting the methods of managing the educational process at school.

Pedagogical theory in this case determines how to act according to the education of students, but does not show how to do this without replacing the practical work of the teacher with research. There are also no tools for managing the learning process that guarantee the result, because it is difficult to determine what exactly was learned and what the result will be in the

practical activity of the teacher. Only a technologically cultured teacher with cognitive ability, flexibility and mobility is able to work in extraordinary conditions; can actively realize his creative abilities and rich personal potential [2].

Acquisition of technological culture by future foreign language teachers allows them to creatively determine the best ways to solve problems that arise using modern technologies.

The technological culture of a foreign language teacher is a set of elements that combines the technological knowledge and skills necessary for the successful mastering of changing activities, as well as personal qualities of professional importance, which gives you a pedagogical enables the successful design and introduction of technologies into the educational process. It is necessary to talk about what describes the socio-professional mobility of a graduate of a higher educational institution of pedagogy.

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REFERENCES

1. Xorijiy tillarni o'rganishni ommalashtirish faoliyatini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining PQ-5117-son Qarori. 2021 yil 19 may.
2. Коваленко А.В. Технологическая культура будущих учителей иностранного языка // Высшее образование сегодня. 2008. № 3. - С. 75.
3. Коржева Э.М., Наумова Н.Ф. Социальная мобильность и российское общество. - М., 2005. - С. 197.
4. Raximov Z.T. Ta'limning mobillashuvi sharoitida masofaviy o'qitish texnologiyasining uzluksiz rivojlanishi/ Zamonaviy ta'lim 2018, 11-b.
5. Сенько Ю.В. Гуманитарные основы педагогического образования. - М., 2000. - С. 37.
6. <http://www.study.vic.gov.au/deecd/learn/study-in>
7. <http://elearning.zn.uz/>